

Moisture Content Detection Using a (Sub-)Terahertz Handheld Device

Karoline FELBERMAYER¹, Sandrine VAN FRANK¹, Elisabeth LEISS-HOLZINGER¹, Robert ZIMMERLEITER¹, Clemens HESCH¹
¹ RECENDT GmbH, Linz, Austria, karoline.felbermayer@recendt.at

Abstract. Moisture significantly influences the performance and longevity of various materials, especially those derived from bio-based sources. High moisture levels can foster microbial growth and cause dimensional instability, while overly dry conditions may lead to brittleness and cracking. In outdoor environments, fluctuating humidity cycles present a major challenge, often accelerating the degradation of bio-based products.

Traditional methods for measuring moisture content are often invasive, introducing heat or mechanical stress that may alter the material, or limited to surface-level analysis. In contrast, (sub-)terahertz ((sub-)THz) technology offers a non-destructive, contactless alternative. Terahertz waves are particularly sensitive to water content, making (sub-)THz sensing a promising tool for moisture detection across a wide range of applications, including bio-based composite panels.

Initial studies used THz spectroscopic analysis in transmission geometry to develop a methodology for quantifying moisture from two-dimensional datasets. However, due to practical constraints of transmission-based setups, the focus shifted to reflection-mode sensing. A dedicated test system was designed and thoroughly evaluated, enabling comparative analysis between the proposed THz-based approach and conventional moisture detection techniques.

Building on these insights, a portable prototype device was developed for in-situ moisture assessment, particularly in outdoor environments. This handheld sub-THz sensor marks a significant step forward in material diagnostics, offering a complementary and practical alternative to traditional methods, especially for monitoring bio-based materials under dynamic environmental conditions.

Keywords: Moisture, THz, sub-THz, bio-based materials

Introduction

Fossil-based materials are increasingly replaced by bio-based materials for a transition towards a green and circular economy. Developing novel bio-based products for urban outdoor applications through innovative characterization, digital technologies, and circular approach is the aim of the EU founded project AMBIANCE. The durability and mechanical stability of bio-based products for outdoor use depend heavily on natural climatic factors, such as sunlight or moisture.

Moisture has a big impact on the long-term stability of bio-based materials, such as the straw bio-based decorative panels, which are an experimental development by RISE in the AMBIANCE project. As innovative characterization method THz was chosen to measure the moisture content of these panels in outdoor use. Because water is a polar molecule that strongly absorbs Terahertz (THz) radiation [1]. Measurements of moisture content employing THz radiation are, in the absence of significant scattering, dominated by absorption due to moisture content and are relatively immune to small fluctuations in the concentration of other constituents [2]. This makes THz radiation a very good candidate for a simple, beyond-state-of-the-art moisture sensor. THz technology is contactless, non-destructive, and allows measurements of moisture content in the bulk with minimal calibration. Previous studies have shown the potential of THz radiation for measuring the moisture content of plant leaves [2], [3], wood [4], [5], paper [6], plastic packages [7], crushed wheat grains [8] and food wafers [9].

1. Development steps – From lab to prototype

1.1 Evaluation of the frequency range

The first step was employing broadband THz spectroscopy to identify the ideal frequency range for measurements. This range can vary depending on the bio-based material, thickness, pore size, and the required spatial resolution. To do so, we conducted THz spectral measurements on wood samples (HIPWOOD) from RISE, as shown in **Figure 1 right**.

Figure 1. left and middle: Photos of the fast time domain THz imaging setup for spectral analysis (TeraFlash from Toptica, with RECENDT imaging extension) and **right:** photo of the wood sample (HIPWOOD) from RISE and 2D THz-maxima transmission scanning image.

THz measurements were conducted using a time-domain THz system TeraFlash from TOPTICA in transmission mode as shown in **Figure 1 left and middle**. This system presents a broad bandwidth (0.05-6 THz), allowing us to figure out over a broad range of frequencies which part(s) of the THz spectrum is/are best suited for the intended moisture evaluation. Lower frequencies typically penetrate deeper into materials, while higher frequencies allow a better resolution. Compact, single frequency sources also have a price tag that increases with frequency. Ultimately, the choice of frequency is a trade-off between these three key aspects.

Figure 2. THz-pulse signal and THz-spectrum of a HIPWOOD sample, with the reference pulse and spectrum in air (red), as well as the signals and spectra determined from dry (orange) and wet (blue) samples.

In **Figure 2** the spectrum of air (red) as a reference, alongside the distinctive spectra of a dry sample (orange) and a wet sample (blue) is presented. The results indicate that the bio-based wood samples show significant attenuation in the higher end of the THz range but allows for good transmission in the lower sub-THz range, around 0.1-0.7 THz. A marked difference between the dry and the wet samples was seen, with the wet sample absorbing significantly more THz radiation than the dry sample over the whole spectral range, which is also true for lower frequencies.

Based on these findings, the focus of the efforts on the lower part of the THz spectrum, which provides higher penetration depth into the material and is detectable using more compact and cost-effective hardware.

1.2 Evaluation of equipment

In view of developing a user-friendly, handheld demonstrator for moisture evaluation in various locations, a 100 GHz source and the 2D THz camera from TeraSense were chosen.

The camera can record a two-dimensional THz intensity image. Illustrations of both dry and wet HIPWOOD THz intensity images are presented in **Figure 3** below, clearly demonstrating the distinction between the dry and wet conditions.

Figure 3. 48 x 48 mm² Images of HIPWOOD samples as evaluated using the TeraSense Camera. **Left:** dry sample; **Right:** wet sample.

The Tera-1024 from TeraSense is a 2D THz camera consists of a 32x32 array (1024 pixels) with a 1.5-pixel pitch and a frequency range from 10 GHz to 1 THz. The sub-THz wave source is based on IMPATT diodes with a frequency of 100 GHz and 80 mW output rf power.

For the evaluation process, python programs were written to access and analyse the 2D THz raw data and automated measurement. The in-house developed software allows performing automated measurements over days, measure co-registered data of two THz cameras, comparing reflection and transmission data, sweep through a range of pre-selectable exposure-times, co-registered data of a moisture scale and save the corresponding data along with timestamps and meta-data. Though for reasons of readability called “reflection” mode, the underlying physical principle is “transflection”. The THz radiation is not just reflected on the surface of the sample, but part of the THz radiation goes through the material where it experiences absorption, gets reflected on the back surface and propagates towards the detector.

2. Method for moisture estimation with sub-THz data

To set up an effective method for estimating moisture using THz technology, we designed a series of measurements employing both THz and reference techniques and implemented. The samples were indirectly exposed to moisture over an extended duration, allowing for multiple measurements to track changes. The drying process of the samples in a controlled environment while also examining their response to direct exposure to water droplets were meticulously documented. Additionally, we conducted long-term assessments on completely dry samples, watching increasing moisture content due to the indoor humidity level. Wood and straw-based samples supplied by RISE and PODCOMP, along with cut-outs from wood fibre boards commonly used in construction, were used as samples (seen in **Figure 4**) for the evaluation.

Figure 4. **left:** wood samples from RISE; **middle:** cut samples from standard construction wooden boards; **right:** barley and reed grass samples from RISE.

2.1. Reference methods

2.1.1 Material moisture u (relative to the dry mass):

The oven-drying method (or loss-on-drying, LOD) is generally considered the gold standard for moisture determination. The moisture of solid materials is expressed by the percentage of water relative to the material’s dry mass. We chose this approach as the reference method and applied it in the evaluation of the THz measurement technique.

The material moisture u [%] indicates the water content of the material and is calculated as follows:

$$u [\%] = \frac{(mass_{wet} - mass_{dry})}{mass_{dry}} \cdot 100$$

$mass_{wet}$: Mass of the material sample (= $mass_{water} + mass_{dry}$)

$mass_{water}$: Mass of water contained in the material sample

$mass_{dry}$: Mass of the material sample when fully dry

The mass-moisture determinations were conducted using a KERN PNJ 3000-2M scale. We also attempted to measure mass-moisture during a drying process with a moisture scale from Sartorius. However, this scale emitted high levels of heat radiation, which significantly affected the performance of the TeraSense camera and source. The dry mass refers to the sample being dried in the oven and cooled down inside a desiccator, as all long-term measurements were performed at room temperature.

2.1.2 Moisture content with NIR-micro-spectrometer:

Figure 5. Photography of a RECENDT-NIR-micro-spectrometer

NIR spectroscopy is an effective tool for analysis of moisture levels, providing a non-invasive and rapid approach [10]. RECENDT has developed an in-house method for estimating moisture content using a cost-effective tuneable Fabry-Pérot filter-based near-infrared (NIR) micro-spectrometer (see **Figure 5**) [11]. The NIR spectrometer used for moisture detection covers the wavelength region 1750 – 2150 nm which covers the strong absorption peak of water around 1930 nm (H-O-H bending and O-H asymmetric stretching combination band) which allows accurate detection of water. To measure the sample moisture, first an NIR spectrum of the sample is acquired with subsequent standard normal variate (SNV) normalisation to remove scattering artefacts. Two wavelength regions are then chosen from the acquired NIR spectrum, one strongly influenced by sample moisture close to the maximum of the water absorption, and another one as a reference. By calculation of the quotient of the absorbance value at these two wavelengths, the sample moisture can be accurately determined. Therefore, such a sensor system has already been successfully implemented for moisture measurement in a production line. Anyway, due to the limited penetration depth of NIR radiation in wood-like materials, sub-surface moisture detection is limited to a sub-mm penetration depth. In addition, any illumination in the (near-)infrared range unavoidably heats the sample. This causes drying especially of stationary samples which limits the non-interrupted observation time significantly and must be considered regarding evaluation and calibration. Due to the lower energy transfer into the investigated sample, THz radiation is superior in terms of long-term observation of drying processes as well as penetration depth.

2.2. THz method evaluation:

In **Figure 6** the photos illustrate the THz-setups at different stages of development. On the left, the THz-camera and source are positioned in transmission. In the middle, the experimental reflection setup to find the fitting angle and distance is shown. The final lab setup with a Kern scale for moisture content measurements are on the right side.

Figure 6. Photos showing the development steps of the moisture assessment setup, with the THz camera and sub-THz source used for the prototype. **Left:** Transmission; **middle:** first reflection; **right:** final lab setup with a Kern scale.

The initial tests were conducted using transmission methods and yielded positive results, demonstrating a method for using THz 2D images to show moisture in the sample, as illustrated in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7. Moisture test measurement with two HIPWOOD samples 1 and 2 in transmission with the THz-camera and sub-THz source and compared to the mass-moisture measurement.

Evaluation is based on the “Beer-Lambert Law” and using the image data from the transmission measurement to determine the material moisture u [%]:

$$u[\%] = \log\left(\frac{I_{dry}}{I_{wet}}\right) \cdot k$$

By using the THz camera, the mean value of the THz intensity I_{wet} is calculated over the 2D image. A previously established mean value I_{dry} from a dry sample is used for “uncalibrated” calculations. The term is then multiplied by the calibration factor k (e.g. calibrating with the mass-moisture content or the thickness and density of the material), which will give the calibrated moisture content. However, for outdoor applications, measuring in transmission would often be impractical. This fact led to further exploration of

a solution for moisture evaluation in reflection. In the new configuration, the THz beam is reflected on the surface of the sample at an angle of 47° and 11 mm from the camera. The material moisture $u[\%]$ was determined using the same computational approach applied in the transmission measurements. This method demonstrated robust repeatability, particularly within the lower moisture range. In reflection mode, the model becomes more complex, due to the nature of transfection. Higher water content has two counteracting effects on the level of detected radiation. On the one hand, it means higher absorption, leading to a decrease of radiation, as shown by the equations for transmission presented above. On the other hand, water droplets or high moisture layers act as mirror, leading to more THz radiation being reflected towards the detector. Experimental observations have shown that the calibration factor k depends on the thickness and density of the material and requires further investigation for different materials.

3. Description of prototype and evaluation measurements

After the evaluation of the equipment and the positioning, a prototype housing was designed in solidEdge and 3D printed with ecoPLA with a Prusa 3D printer, shown in **Figure 8**. The special design is based on the estimated distance and angle of the lab setup. The prototype was designed so that it can be easily operated with a power bank for upcoming outdoor applications. But it can also be installed in the laboratory or in a production plant with a fixed power supply.

Figure 8. left: the CAD-image of the sub-THz-handheld sensor housing; middle and right: photos of the finished sub-THz-handheld sensor including the sub-THz source and camera from TeraSense.

The sub-THz source is the only device that needs a separate power supply, allowing for a more streamlined setup. The THz camera conveniently connects to a laptop via USB, ensuring easy integration and use. This device is intended to be used outside the lab, to detect moisture within the decorative panels, which are produced from our AMBIANCE project partner RISE and PODCOMP. Therefore, the software focuses on real-time visualization in contrast to the command-line based software of the long-term measurements. Currently, the software is implemented as an extension to the TeraView software (a screen shot is shown in **Figure 9**), maximizing efficiency, to become a robust tool for moisture detection.

Figure 9. Screenshot of the User Interface of the prototype

3.1. Evaluation measurements with Mass-Moisture Method (Scales):

As mentioned above, we employed a Kern scale to estimate the mass, which was connected to a laptop through a serial interface. This integration allowed for the development of a measurement script designed for automated data collection, streamlining the process. The results of moisture content measurement on cut-outs from wood fibre boards are shown in **Figure 10**.

Figure 10. Evaluation of moisture content measurements with different 5 exposure times on 5 positions on measured on a cut-out from wood fibre board shown as purple, orange, brown, pink and grey stars (5 different positions) and dashed lines (fitted curve) compared to the simultaneous detected mass moisture content (red)

The moisture procedure started by determining the dry value of the material with the prototype and measuring the weight. This is the basis for the method to calculate the uncalibrated or calibrated moisture content. The sample is then placed in a plastic box on a grid above water, and the box is tightly sealed to ensure indirect moisture exposure. At defined time slots the sample is taken from the box to determine the THz-data at different positions and switching through the chosen exposure times. Simultaneously the weight from the sample is determined. After finishing the long-term moisture evaluation procedure, the data are analysed and plotted in the graphs, where the red dashed line is the mass moisture content of the sample estimated with the reference measurement with the scale. The other coloured (purple, orange, brown, pink and grey) dashed lines are the fitted moisture content calculated from the THz-data with different exposure times and the stars are the analysed data at 5 different measurement position on the wood sample.

3.2. Evaluation measurement with NIR micro-spectrometer:

Because the penetration depth of NIR radiation is limited to the sub-surface, it is not suitable for thicker samples. However, it allowed for valuable insights into moisture penetration coming from the back of the sample. As the measurement progressed, the surface remained dry for an extended duration. The test results, illustrated in **Figure 11** highlight this: the blue curve depicts the uncalibrated moisture content detected by the sub-terahertz handheld device while the red curve showcases the uncalibrated moisture content measured with the micro-spectrometer. This evidence underscores the effectiveness of using the prototype for in-depth moisture analysis.

Figure 11. Detection of water droplets and their penetration in the sample with THz -Prototype (blue) and a micro-spectrometer (red)

The material moisture curve detected with the device (indicated in blue) shows the following: As the waterdrop is put onto the sample, it acts as mirror, and more THz radiation is reflected, and must not be misinterpreted as ‘less absorption’. This ‘low’ moisture ‘spike’ is then followed by a significant increase of moisture at the beginning of the test, followed by a notable decrease after 30 minutes. This decrease is detected by the NIR spectrometer as well, so there was probably a drying effect. A second application, comprised of smaller water droplets on the backside, was also tracked by THz, and showed at first a ‘mirror’ effect, again not to be misinterpreted as ‘low moisture’. As the water penetrates the material, both moisture curves show an upward trend. The test was stopped when the micro-spectrometer's light source began to dry the surface, which distorted the moisture detection. Remarkably, the moisture results of the micro-spectrometer show a gradual increase like the prototype as the water penetrates further into the material. This proves the efficiency of our moisture detection methods under real-time conditions.

4. Conclusion:

In this work, a sub-THz measurement approach was developed, evaluated, and implemented as a promising method for determining moisture content in bio-based construction materials. The study demonstrated that THz radiation—particularly in the lower sub-THz range around 0.1-0.7 THz—offers substantial advantages for moisture sensing due to its strong interaction with water molecules, its capability for bulk measurements, its non-destructive, contactless nature, as well as its low energy transfer.

Broadband laboratory spectroscopy enabled the identification of suitable frequency ranges and confirmed measurable distinctions between dry and wet samples. Based on these findings, compact and cost-effective hardware using a 100 GHz source and a 2D THz camera was selected for prototype development. The resulting handheld device allows for real-time visualisation, straightforward operation, and the potential for outdoor use in monitoring the moisture behaviour of bio-based panels developed within the AMBIANCE project.

Comprehensive evaluation measurements integrating mass-moisture, THz imaging, and NIR micro-spectroscopy validated the THz-based method. Transmission and reflection studies confirmed that moisture content can be reliably estimated from THz intensity data using a Beer–Lambert-type model, although reflection-based measurements require further refinement due to complex transfection effects. Long-term moisture uptake experiments and controlled water droplet tests demonstrated that the prototype could track both surface and subsurface moisture changes. Comparison with NIR measurements provided important confirmation of moisture penetration dynamics and highlighted the added value of the deeper penetration depth offered by THz radiation.

Overall, the results underline the strong potential of sub-THz imaging as an innovative, beyond-state-of-the-art tool for moisture detection in materials, such as bio-based polymers made from wood, straw or grass. Future work will focus on refining calibration methods, improving robustness under outdoor conditions, and extending the method to a broader range of material types and thicknesses. With these developments, the THz-based sensor system can become a valuable component in ensuring durability, quality control, and long-term performance of sustainable bio-based products.

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